

The Disadvantages of using a Monitoring System for Air Quality

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Abstract

Air quality affects human health as well as visibility. Urban activities, particularly automobile traffic, are a significant contributor to environmental pollution, which is harmful to the general public's health. In order to plan and regulate these operations, public authorities and the general public will eventually need to be able to predict air quality in advance in order to limit the detrimental effects on the environment and human health. Advances in sensor technology and artificial intelligence (AI) have made it possible to predict air quality by accounting for a range of environmental factors.

Keywords: Air Quality, Environments, Air Pollution, Safety.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the main issues facing the environment worldwide is air pollution. The World Health Organization [1] reports that population morbidity overall is higher in cities with more polluted air. Due to its detrimental effects on human health and even mortality, particulate matter, particularly tiny particles (PM_{2.5}) with a diameter of 2.5 micrometers or less, is considered one of the most dangerous elements of urban emissions [2–5]. The current scenario is made worse by the positive association that exists between air pollution and the COVID-19 virus's spread. The cornerstone for the virus's long-distance spread is particulate matter (PM). Additionally, PM exacerbates COVID-19 patients' symptoms. In 2020, these data will be published in numerous international papers [6–8]. While PM concentrations decreased significantly during the quarantine period, as demonstrated by Daniella and Leonardo Rodriguez-Urrego [9], air quality monitoring continues to be the most significant activity for scientists worldwide, including those in Ukraine [10]. It is common knowledge that the air we breathe is contaminated. Pollution comes from a variety of sources, particularly in large cities. A number of sensors are in place to keep an eye on air pollution. The Air Quality Index (AQI) is one of the international measures used to track the number of contaminants in urban air. Ground-level ozone, particle pollution, carbon monoxide, sulfur dioxide, and nitrogen dioxide are the five main air pollutants that are measured by air quality sensors. These data are then combined to create the Air Quality Index. Additionally, even though the sensors can't lower air pollution on their own, you can still make suggestive maps of urban pollution using the data they offer [12].

II. RELATED WORKS

Air quality knowledge depends on measurements of the lower atmosphere's vertical structure. Drones, or unmanned aerial systems, can measure temperature, pressure, and relative humidity reliably and at a minimal cost. On a UAS, a set of low-cost sensors managed by an Arduino microprocessor board were compared to a meteorological-grade sensor. A forward-moving sampler and a vertical ascension sampler were the two sampling modalities investigated. Vertical aerosol distributions during an inversion event might be retrieved with the integration of a tiny particle sensor (Sensiron SPS30). The temperature probe based on thermocouples and the Bosch BME280 sensor's relative humidity measurement showed strong correlations with the meteorological sensor. Then, on a platform that made a rocket-like sound, the temperature and relative humidity sensors were installed. The rocket sounding mechanism worked effectively up to 400 meters in altitude. It was discovered that the low-cost sensors functioned well enough for low-cost development and

application in research and teachings [13]. This paper provides an innovative approach to air quality prediction and examines how it relates to various urban activities and environmental conditions, including traffic density. In order to accomplish this goal, we integrate traffic density from closed-circuit television footage and real-time data from several environmental sensors into a multi-modal framework that we propose. Within a streaming dataset, the framework efficiently handles data discrepancies caused by malfunctioning cameras and sensors. The dataset displays complicated real-world features such as outliers, noise interference, and sudden camera or station activations or deactivations. By applying a particle swarm optimization (PSO)-based merit fusion of the sensor data to train a joint model on data from adjacent stations and sensors, the proposed approach addresses the problem of predicting air quality at places without sensors or with malfunctioning sensors. Several LSTM model variants, such as bi-directional LSTM, CNN-LSTM, and convolutional LSTM (ConvLSTM), are used to test the suggested technique. The results show an improvement over the ARIMA model of 48%, 67%, and 173% for short-, medium-, and long-term periods, respectively. The quantity of airborne particulate matter (PM) in the ferroalloy sector can be rather high, which is concerning for both the environment and occupational health. In recent years, there has been interest in small, inexpensive sensors that measure PM, which allow for extensive monitoring of PM levels in the environment. These sensors haven't, however, been thoroughly tested in environments comparable to the metallurgical industry's indoor spaces. By comparing the low-cost, commercial Nova PM SDS011 particle sensor in two distinct ferroalloy plants, this study seeks to close this gap. The Fidas 200S, which has undergone suitable testing and certification in compliance with the most recent EU regulations (EN 15267, EN 16450), was used as the benchmark. A silicomanganese alloy (SiMn) plant tested twelve Nova sensors over the course of three months, while a silicon (Si) plant tested thirty-five sensors in a single month. The findings demonstrated that while the low-cost Nova sensors reported lower dust concentrations than the Fidas 200S, they had all the same trends and peaks in terms of PM concentration. The higher measurement range of the Fidas, measuring down to 180 nm compared to the Nova, which measures down to 300 nm, and the size and mass percentages of particles in Si dust compared to SiMn dust are the reasons for the larger discrepancy, which was expected, at the silicon plant. The data from the Nova sensors was found to be useful for comparing dust levels over time for various operations, at various locations, and under various operating conditions, notwithstanding the differences in absolute numbers [14]. Historically, costly measurement apparatus has been used in a small number of permanent locations to conduct conventional air quality monitoring. When hot spots are absent, for example, the resulting sparse spatial air quality data does not accurately reflect the actual air quality of the entire region. This project focused on creating an affordable network of cloud-based air quality measuring systems in order to acquire air quality data with improved spatial and temporal resolution. These platforms ought to be capable of measuring the following factors related to air quality: air temperature, relative humidity, gases like NO, NO₂, O₃, and CO, and particle matter (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁). On average, these parameters were recorded every minute and sent to a cloud server every second. The platform created for this study processed, read, and stored sensor data in the cloud using a single main computer. Three prototypes were put to the test in real-world settings: two in the busy Marienplatz traffic site in Stuttgart, and one at a remote location in Ötisheim where measurements were taken close to active railroad tracks. The designed platform proved to be reliable during the measurement phase and had material costs for one air quality sensor node of about 1500 euros. It was also investigated whether a dryer could function more effectively by using a proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controller, which would lessen the adverse impact of climatic factors like air temperature and relative humidity on the measurement outcomes. This is thought to be one method of raising the caliber of data that inexpensive sensors are able to collect [15]. Whether indoors or out, preserving human health and well-being depends on monitoring air quality (AQ). Particulate matter (PM) is one of the most important metrics that needs to be checked on a regular basis. Poor spatial and temporal AQ information results from the high cost and difficulty of deploying traditional reference particulate analyzers on a broad scale. But it's still unclear how accurate and dependable these sensors are. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of five inexpensive sensors for air quality (AQ) monitoring in compliance with US EPA recommendations by contrasting them with a particle reference analyzer. SLR models, or basic linear regression, were used to assess the sensors in both indoor and outdoor conditions. The findings show that inexpensive sensors cannot be relied upon to measure air quality correctly indoors. During the three-week analysis period, for a 1-hour average, the coefficient of determination (R²) values ranged from 0.2 to 0.58, indicating a weak correlation between the sensors and the reference analyzer. With an R² value of 0.72, the sensor (HPMA115) did, however, meet the US EPA-recommended standard after increasing the average time interval. Certain sensors' root-mean-square error (RMSE) values were higher than the US EPA's recommended threshold of less than 7 µg/m³ for PM sensors. Temperature, indoor relative humidity (RH), and PM_{2.5} concentration were found to have possible influences on sensor behavior. Variations in RH and temperature were noted between testing with and without occupants, indicating that the air conditioning system also had an impact on the sensor's function. The outcomes demonstrated that inexpensive sensors, like Honeywell's HPMA115, may be used in outdoor settings. But the calibration procedure needs to be carried out for every unique environment. Our research revealed the shortcomings of inexpensive sensors for air quality monitoring and the necessity of additional study to create trustworthy sensors [16, 17]. Urban air pollution is a major problem that necessitates effective air quality management to maintain acceptable health levels. By expanding the spatial distribution of ambient air quality monitoring—a task that can be accomplished with inexpensive sensors—the hotspots can be found. It is widely acknowledged that numerous factors impact their outcomes, nevertheless. High relative humidity can significantly affect the quality of data obtained from low-cost Particulate Matter

(PM) sensors. To mitigate the effects of elevated relative humidity on the outcomes derived from inexpensive PM sensors, a low-cost dryer was created and its efficacy was examined. A test chamber was developed for this purpose, and professional reference devices and inexpensive PM sensors were added. The test chamber's relative humidity was controlled via a vaporizer. Depending on the voltage, the inexpensive dryer heated the sample air to a manually controlled temperature. To determine the ideal voltage with the lowest energy usage and the highest drying efficiency, several voltages were evaluated. We evaluated the inexpensive PM sensors with and without the inexpensive dryer. The outcomes of the experiment confirmed that the low-cost dryer's use lessened the impact of relative humidity on the low-cost PM sensor readings [18].

III. IMPORTANT BENEFITS OF AIR QUALITY MONITORING

The following are some significant advantages of monitoring air quality.

1. We are able to evaluate the effects of poor air quality on public health thanks to the data gathered from air quality monitoring.
2. Data on air quality allows us to assess if a certain location is satisfying the CPCB, WHO, or OSHA air quality guidelines.
3. We would mainly be able to identify polluted locations, the amount of pollution, and the level of air quality with the use of data gathered from air quality monitoring.
4. Monitoring the quality of the air would help assess the effectiveness of localized air pollution management initiatives.
5. We can better comprehend the death rate from air pollution in any given location by using statistics on air quality. The short- and long-term illnesses and disorders brought on by air pollution can also be evaluated and contrasted.
6. Control measures for the preservation of the environment and the wellbeing of all living things can be developed based on the data gathered [19].

IV. THE DISADVANTAGES OF USING A MONITORING SYSTEM FOR AIR QUALITY

1. The air is not cleaned by an air quality sensor.
2. The source of the contaminants is not displayed.
3. A consumer-grade monitor typically costs \$150.
4. Carbon monoxide (CO) is not typically measured by air quality devices.
5. Both dangerous and safe substances are included in the measured VOCs.
6. It can take up to seven days for air quality monitors to calibrate [21].

CONCLUSION

We've looked over a number of studies pertaining to air quality, observed technological developments in the area, and discussed some important benefits of air quality monitoring systems [20]. A thorough discussion of a monitoring and control system's drawbacks is also included.

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